

PEER- REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education Research
Journal (AMIERJ)
ISSN 2278-5655***

Impact Factor :0.948

Bi-Monthly

VOL - II

ISSUES - V

[2013-14]

**Chief-
Editor:**

**U b a l e
A m o l
B a b a n**

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near TV Towar,Badlapur, MS

TECHNIQUES TO BOOST CREATIVITY AMONG CHILDREN

Suryawanshi Milind

Principal,

Zeal Education Society's

Dnyanganaga College of Education,

Pune

Abstract

Creativity is a great power of human beings, just because of creative thinking impossible is made possible. Many inventions and innovations are the product of the creativity. It is said that whatever invention we see at first it takes place in the mind. It is a foremost thing that we must train the children about how to think. Children must have the knowledge about creative ideas and various techniques by which creative thinking can be developed. With the help of various techniques and strategies creativity can be developed among children. Inductive thinking, synectic model, brain storming and many more strategies can be used to develop creativity among children. In the present paper such strategies are discussed.

Introduction-

In every field creative person is very valuable and plays vital role because he gives unique ideas and solution for the problems. Psychologist proved that any person can be creative if the proper training and opportunities of creative thinking are given to them. Creative persons think in various dimensions he/she appropriately study the facts, information and give the output in a very different manner. Creative person joins the components of the facts in a unique way and brought solution proves practically useful and relevant. Creative person is a valuable asset of the organization. Keeping all these things in the mind from the beginning teachers, parents must give

opportunity for the creative problem solving. Teachers must have knowledge of various techniques through which creativity can be developed. Following are some of the technique through which w can boost creativity among students.

About Creativity-

The Latin word *creatio* was originally applied solely to deeds of God. Only later, in The Renaissance Period – when man first recognized his own ability to create something new into existence – the word creativity became used for describing human accomplishments.

According to James M. Higgins, creativity is the process of generating something new that has value.

Robert E. Franklin- Creativity is defined as the tendency to generate or recognize ideas, alternatives, or possibilities that may be useful in solving problems, communicating with others and entertaining ourselves and others.

A number of personality traits have been shown to be associated with creative productivity. A high degree of self-confidence is a basic need for an individual that aims to create something new, so is unconventional thought and curiosity. In order to practice creativity, one must be a master of his particular field, while also having the self-sufficiency to explore and the flexibility to step outside of the box.

Inductive thinking, divergent thinking and thinking out of routine pattern are prerequisite for the creativity.

Methods for Boost Creativity-

Brainstorming

This technique has evolved by Alex Osborn, in the group also and at the individual level also this technique can be used effectively. This technique is discussed by Osborn in the book ‘Applied Imagination’.

The Brainstorming process starts off with the problem clearly stated and recognized by all participants. One person out of the group is chosen to write down all the ideas that are suggested in order to make them at the same time visible to all others.

The Brainstormers suggest solution to the problem, starting from very evident answers, and often going to the great. Criticizing suggested solutions is not allowed. Every idea is accepted and written down. It works in collaborative way all participants are needed to develop each others' ideas.

Lateral Thinking

Lateral Thinking is a creative technique that encourages reasoning that is not immediately noticeable, and ideas that may not be obtainable by using only traditional step-by-step logic. It is about **finding a solution to problems through an indirect approach.**

Edward de Bono, who coined the term Lateral Thinking (acknowledged in the Oxford English Dictionary), is regarded by many as the leading authority in the field of creative thinking, innovation and the direct teaching of thinking as a skill. De Bono claims that it is important to disrupt the conventional patterns adopted by the brain. In notes from definition on Lateral Thinking, De Bono states: "Lateral Thinking is used for changing concepts and perceptions instead of trying harder with the same concepts and perceptions".

To demonstrate this form of thinking, take for example a simple problem like opening a door. Now think of some new solution except the doorknob. This forces you to think about creative solutions that are close to or the extreme opposite of a doorknob. It promotes thinking outside of the box.

Albert Einstein, whose name is a synonym for genius of originality and creativity, once said: "*The problems of today will not be solved by the same thinking that produced the problems in the first place*".

Problem Reversal

According to Charles Thompson Problem Reversal is a one of the best way to truly understand this world is to learn from positives as well as from negatives. Summer-Winter, Day-Night, love-hate are just some examples of that.

Problem reversal method is based on **stating the problem in reverse**. Change a positive statement into a negative one. Next, try to define what something is not, change the direction or location of one's perspective.

Concept Mapping

Concept maps represent knowledge graphic form. Networks consist of various items, which represent concepts, and links, which represent relationships between concepts.

Concept maps can aid in generating ideas, designing complex structures, or communicating complex ideas. Because they make explicit the integration of old and new knowledge concept maps can help instructors assess students' understanding. Holistic and clear picture of the concept can be brought in to view with the help of concept map. Old, new, creative ideas can be integrated meaningfully in this technique. This method allows students to see the interconnections, how one idea relates to another, and how pieces come together. Once the ideas flow, students become immersed in the.

Role-playing

Situations or individual issues ,problems can be focused in most role-playing exercises, each student takes the role of a person affected by an issue and studies an issue or events from the perspective of that person. Role playing gives insight to the person about how the situation can be changed with better solutions.

Role plays should give the students an opportunity to practice what they have learned and should interest the students.

Provide concrete information and clear role descriptions so that students can play their roles with confidence.

Story Writing Exercise-

This exercise can be operated on a group or an individual. In this exercise some pictures are shown to the children and the students are asked to build a story around it. Instead of pictures song (which students don't know) also can be used but the song must contain some plot or story. At the end children are asked to write the hidden story or the concept.

Image Streaming –

This exercise can be carried out on a pair of students. The student, who exercises, closes his/her eyes and asks to narrate what he/she is visualizing. The exercising student then describes out louder mental visual imagery either to another student or tape recorder. Describing of mental images should be flowing and streaming, while doing so, students should concentrate on his/her sensory elements. I.e. I feel, I am standing on a hot tile, I am standing on a wet soil, etc. In order to develop and maintain flow of streaming imagery student should go on asking him/her another question and this process should be repeated.

Synecitic Model-

Willam Gardon has designed this model. This model is very useful to develop creativity among children. The model includes creative problem solving, brainstorming, direct analogy, persona analogy, analogy contrast. E.g in the analogy contrast(paradox) gives different critical angles to a creative idea; e.g. losing- winner, open-secret, wise-fool, bitter-sweet etc. At their most basic level, a paradox is a statement that is self contradictory because it often contains two statements that are both true but in general cannot be true at the same time. This model has the ability to awaken the “creative thinker” in every student.

References-

Anderson, H.H, Creativity and its Cultivation,Harper & Row ,Publishers, New York,1959

Gardon, Willam, Synectics, Collier—Mackmillan Ltd,London

R. J., Torff, B., & Grigorenko, E. L. Teaching triarchically improves school achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology.*

Sternberg, R. J., & Williams, W. M. (1996). *How to develop student creativity.* Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.

Sternberg, R. J., Torff, B.,& Grigorenko, E. L. (1998). Teaching for successful intelligence raises school achievement.

Sternberg, R. J., Kaufman, J. C., & Pretz, J. E. (2002). *The creativity conundrum.* New York: Psychology Press.

Tetewsky, S. J.,&Sternberg, R. J. (1986). Conceptual and lexical determinants of nonentrenched thinking. *Journal of Memory and Language.*

Torrance, E. P. (1962). *Guiding creative talent.* Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

www.creativityforlife.com

www.ifepositive.com

www.csun.edu